

Urinary schistosomiasis: Health seeking behaviour among residents of Kiri in Shelleng Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The survey was designed to study community's knowledge and health care seeking behaviour on urinary schistosomiasis in Kiri, Shelleng Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria, due to observation that urinary schistosomiasis is on the increase because of inadequate control strategy. Two hundred and sixty four respondents were randomly selected and interviewed on the causes of urinary schistosomiasis and health-seeking behaviour through a structured questionnaires. Results obtained showed that respondents of secondary level (42.8%) mentioned bathing in contaminated water as the correct medium for the transmission of urinary schistosomiasis. Seventy five percent of the respondents had no idea on the mode of transmission of the disease. Females respondents within the age brackets of 16-20 years (100.0%) and 21-25 years (100.0%) had higher contacts with water on each day due to daily domestic needs. Management of haematuria were majorly based on visiting patent medicine store (29.5%), herbalist (17.0%) and drug vendors (11.4%). Many (37.5%) of the respondents do not seek for medical intervention. Educational awareness affected the respondents' knowledge on the correct drug used for the treatment of urinary schistosomiasis. About 83.0% had no idea on chemotherapy used for the treatment of urinary schistosomiasis. None of the respondents was able to mention praziquantel as the correct drug used for the treatment of the disease. There is the need to educate the drug vendors and patent medicine store owners, the point at which people in rural communities get their medication for the treatment of the disease. These findings will be used for proper health education and planning to reduce to the barest minimum urinary schistosomiasis among Kiri community.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Schistosomiasis is a parasitic disease caused by blood flukes (trematodes) of the genus *Schistosoma* [1]. Infection is acquired when people come in contact with fresh water infested with the larval forms (cercariae) of parasitic blood flukes, known as schistosomes, often through daily activities such as bathing, washing laundry, and fetching [2].

The disease is classified as a neglected tropical disease of poverty that leads to chronic ill-health [3,4]. More than 207 million people, 85% who live in Africa, are infected with urinary schistosomiasis in communities where portable

water and sanitation are inadequate [5]. At present, an estimated 700 million people are at risk of infection in 76 countries where the disease is considered endemic [6], as their agricultural work, domestic chores, and recreational activities expose them to infested water [7,8].

Refugee movements due to insecurity and urban drift are introducing the disease to new locations where it has not existed. Increasing population size and needs for irrigation farming, hydroelectric power and water supply have open many ways to increased transmission of the disease. Infections are not uniformly distributed within communities because of differences in

knowledge, attitudes and practices on hygiene [9]. An endemic community may be heavily infected, especially among those who lived near lakes, rivers or dams where water activities are daily carried out [10].

Signs and symptoms of schistosomiasis may include abdominal pain, diarrhoea, bloody stool, or blood in the urine. From ancient times to the early 20th century, the beliefs in schistosomiasis' symptom of blood in urine was thus viewed as a sign of maturity for boys. Some communities beliefs in Nigeria indicated that walking on hot sun, eating too much salt, violation of taboos of the ancestors, bad blood and dirtiness were the sole cause of schistosomiasis [11,12].

Schistosomiasis is treatable using a single dose of the drug praziquantel by mouth annually. Other possible treatments include a combination of praziquantel with metrifonate, artesunate or mefloquine. A Cochrane review found tentative evidence that when used alone metrifonate was as effective as praziquantel. Another agent, mefloquine, which has previously been used to treat malaria, was recognised in 2008–2009 to be effective against schistosoma. Mefloquine may be used in combination with praziquantel or artemisinins [13,14,15]. However, in Nigeria different treatments are sought for schistosomiasis especially in communities where the disease is endemic. Akinwale et. al. [12] reported the pattern of health seeking behaviour of some communities in Niger and Abeokuta indicated that 35% , 3.2%, 30%, 1.8%, 59% used government clinics, private clinics, chemist, indigenous healers, religious healers and orthodox treatment respectively.

There is serious Paucity of knowledge on health seeking behaviour and causes of urinary schistosomiasis even within the same ethnic and geographical location, perception differs about the disease [16]. While the disease is associated with water as medium for transmission, still many did not know the mode of transmission because of ignorance [17,18]. People still defaecate and urinate near rivers, lakes and dams, thereby increasing the epidemiology of urinary schistosomiasis. Many do not even go to health facilities to receive treatment because of different beliefs associated with the disease.

It is not known whether communities living at Kiri dam in Adamawa State Nigeria, who depend on fishing as a sole base of their economy have knowledge on the mode of transmission, causes, symptoms and treatment of urinary schistosomiasis. This work is aimed at providing information on behaviour of resident of Kiri living with urinary schistosomiasis with regard to knowledge and health-seeking behaviour on urinary schistosomiasis.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study area

The study area was Kiri community located in Shelleng Local Government Area of Adamawa State. Shelleng is situated along latitude 9° 53'51N and longitude 12° 0'32E greenwich meridian with population of 148, 490 [19]. It shares borders with Borno State to the north, Song L.G.A to the East, Demsa L.G.A to the south and Guyuk L.G.A to the West. Kiri dam is situated in Shelleng L.G.A. The dam was constructed in 1982 for the purpose of irrigation, hydroelectric power generation and water supply to Savannah Sugar company Numan. The major water supply to the dam is from Dadin Kowa dam in Gombe State, and it is a tributary to river Benue via River Gongola. The population around the Kiri dam consists of cluster of compounds each surrounded by local made mats and mud wall. The compounds are situated 50-100 metres away from the dam. The main occupation is mainly fishing with a small number of the population engaged in petty trading and cattle rearing. Crop production is difficult in the area because of crashes of hippopotamus from the dam that usually engage in the destruction of crops. The fishermen are mainly Kanakuru. There are also other tribes, like the lunguda, Bachama, Hausa, Bura, Jukun and Jenjo. The inhabitants come in contact with the dam on daily basis for different purposes including fishing, bathing, washing and collecting water for domestic use. There is no health clinic and sanitary infrastructure such as clean drinking water and latrine, if present they are poorly constructed. The only borehole available is competitive and is controlled. In preference the dam is used by residents for different purposes. As a result of poor sanitary infrastructure most people defaecate and urinate indiscriminately thereby contaminating the environment near the dam. With an open vegetation of shrubs and herbaceous plants much favoured by animals, the closeness of Savannah Sugar Company that provides foliage for animal use; the dam is conducive for the nomadic Fulani in dry season and serves as a major campsite and stop post in the nomadic North-South migration.

2.2 Data collection

2.2.1 Administration of questionnaires

Data for the study were collected through structured questionnaires on residents knowledge and health-seeking behaviour. The interviewer administered these questionnaires to 264 randomly selected residents. Biodata were first recorded for each respondents, which include age, sex, educational level attained. There after, the structured questionnaires were administered to them; on causes, treatment, water contact and health-seeking behaviour. Under-five children were interviewed through their parents/guardians.

2.3 Ethical Consideration

The study received approval from Adamawa state, Ministry of Environment and Rural Development, and Shelleng Local government

primary health care. Consent was obtained from each volunteer before the commencement of data and sample collection.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data were entered into a database created in Epidata version 3.1. data was then transferred to statistical analysis system (SAS) version 8.0 and were analysed. Statistical significant difference were indicated by $p < 0.05$ and no statistical difference by $P > 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Demography

Result in Table 1 shows that there were a total of 264 respondents from which 192 were male and 72 were female. The distribution of the respondents by age groups showed that 18.2% were between the age brackets of 16-20 and >30 years respectively. Females and males respondents between the age groups of 6-10 years (29.1%) and 16-20 years (23.4%) respectively were higher than other age groups. While those of age bracket 26-30 years were the least in number (5.7%).

Table 1. Distribution of respondents by age group and sex

Age group (Years)	Respondents					
	Number			Percentages		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
0-5	27	12	39	14.0	16.6	14.8
6-10	21	21	42	10.9	29.1	15.9
11-15	18	15	33	9.3	20.8	12.5
16-20	45	3	48	23.4	4.1	18.2
21-25	36	3	39	18.7	4.1	14.8
26-30	12	3	15	6.2	4.1	5.7
>30	33	15	48	17.2	20.8	18.2
Total	192	72	264	100.0	100.0	100.0

3.2 Knowledge on transmission of urinary schistosomiasis

Result in Table 2 shows respondents perceived causes of urinary schistosomiasis by educational qualification. Forty one percent (41.0%) of the respondents were uneducated, 33.0% had their secondary education. Whereas the least respondents were those of Koranic (4.5%) and Tertiary (2.3%) education. Respondents of secondary level (42.8%) mentioned bathing in contaminated water as one the correct transmission medium for urinary schistosomiasis. Others who mentioned bathing with contaminated water as means of transmission of urinary schistosomiasis were those who had primary education and uneducated people (28.6% each) respectively. Respondents of secondary level, tertiary level and uneducated mentioned water/badfood/sunshine (100.0%), water/mosquito (100.0%) and salt (100.0%) respectively as the cause of urinary schistosomiasis. Seventy five percent (75.0%) of the respondents that are uneducated had no idea on the medium of transmission for urinary schistosomiasis. Analysis of the result confirms that there was no significant variation between educational qualification and perceived cause of urinary schistosomiasis ($p > 0.05$).

3.3 Water contacts

Result in Table 3 shows respondents daily water

contacts by sex and age. Of the 264 respondents interviewed, 72.7% were males that had contact with water on each day for different purposes, while the remaining 27.2% were females. However, females respondents between age brackets of 16-20 years (100.0%), 21-25 years (100.0%) and 26-30 years (100.0%) had more contacts with water every day than other age groups. The least among females respondents that had contacts with water were between the age brackets of 0-5 years (30.7%) and >30 years (31.2%). Among males respondents, the age groups between 16-20 years (93.7%) were higher followed by 21-25 years (92.3%) and 26-30 years (80.0%). The least among males were between the age group of 6-10 years (46.6%). Those who had contacts with water twice on each day (48.8%) were higher in males as compared to females who had contact with water once every day (33.3%). This is followed by females and males who had contact with water thrice every day (29.1% and 25.0%) respectively.

3.4 Health-care seeking behaviour

Result shows that majority of the treatment received because of haematuria were sought from the patent medicine store (29.5%), hospital (17.0%), herbalist (11.4%), drug vendors (3.4%). Others combine hospital and herbalist (1.1%). A high percentage (37.5%) of the respondents do not seek for medical treatment because of urinary schistosomiasis (Table 4).

Result in Table 5 shows respondents knowledge on treatment of urinary schistosomiasis. About 83.0% of the respondents had no idea on chemotherapy used for treating urinary schistosomiasis. Drugs mentioned by the

respondents for treating urinary schistosomiasis were herbs (7.9%), ampicolox (4.5%), and dapsone (4.5%). None of the respondents were able to mention praziquantel as the correct drug for treating urinary schistosomiasis.

Table 2. Respondents perceived causes of urinary schistosomiasis by educational qualification

Perceived Causes	No. of Respondents	Educational Qualification					Total No. (%)
		Primary No. (%)	Secondary No. (%)	Tertiary No. (%)	Koranic No. (%)	Uneducated No. (%)	
Water/bad food/ sunshine	3	0(0.0)	3(100.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(100.0)
Drinking dirty water	96	24(25.0)	30(31.2)	0(0.0)	6(6.2)	36(37.5)	96(100.0)
Bathing/Drinking dirty water	45	9(20.0)	12(26.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	24(53.3)	45(100.0)
Bathing in dirty water	21	6(28.6)	9(42.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	6(28.6)	21(100.0)
Sunshine/Water	15	0(0.0)	9(60.0)	3(20.0)	0(0.0)	3(20.0)	15(100.0)
Sunshine	33	6(18.2)	15(45.4)	0(0.0)	3(9.1)	9(27.3)	33(100.0)
Salt	9	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	9(100.0)	9(100.0)
Water/Salt	3	0(0.0)	3(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(100.0)
Sunshine/water/Salt	6	3(50.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(50.0)	6(100.0)
Water/Mosquito	3	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(100.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(100.0)
Cold/water/Sunshine	6	0(0.0)	3(50.0)	0(0.0)	3(50.0)	0(0.0)	6(100.0)
No idea	24	3(12.5)	3(12.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	18(75.0)	24(100.0)
Total	264	51(19.3)	87(33.0)	6(2.3)	12(4.5)	108(41.0)	264(100.0)

Table 3. Daily water contacts by sex and age group

Water contacts in a day

Age group (in years)	Number interviewed	Male						Female					
		1 No. (%)	2 No. (%)	3 No. (%)	4 No. (%)	>4 No. (%)	Total No. (%)	1 No. (%)	2 No. (%)	3 No. (%)	4 No. (%)	>4 No. (%)	Total No. (%)
0-5	39	0 (0.0)	15 (55.5)	9 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (11.1)	27 (69.2)	0 (0.0)	3 (25.0)	6 (50)	3 (25.0)	0 (0.0)	12 (30.7)
6-10	45	0 (0.0)	6 (28.5)	9 (42.8)	6 (28.5)	0 (0.0)	21 (46.6)	3 (14.3)	6 (28.5)	9 (42.8)	3 (14.3)	0 (0.0)	21 (46.6)
11-15	30	0 (0.0)	6 (33.3)	6 (33.3)	6 (33.3)	0 (0.0)	18 (60.0)	3 (20.0)	3 (20.0)	6 (40.0)	3 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	15 (50.0)
16-20	48	15 (33.3)	18 (40.0)	9 (20.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (6.6)	45 (93.7)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)
21-25	39	3 (8.3)	15 (41.6)	12 (33.3)	6 (16.6)	0 (0.0)	36 (92.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)
26-30	15	0 (0.0)	6 (40.0)	0 (0.0)	6 (40.0)	0 (0.0)	12 (80.0)	3 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)
>30	48	3 (9.1)	27 (81.8)	3 (9.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	33 (68.7)	15 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	15 (31.2)
Total	264	21 (10.9)	93 (48.8)	48 (25.0)	24 (12.5)	6 (3.1)	192 (72.7)	24 (33.3)	18 (25.0)	21 (29.1)	9 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	72 (27.2)

Table 4. Health seeking behaviour of the respondents

Sources	Number of respondents	Percentage
Hospital	45	17.0
Patent medicine store	78	29.5
Herbalist	30	11.4
Drug vendors	9	3.4
Hospital/Herbalist	3	1.1
No treatment	99	37.5
Total	264	100.0

Table 5. Respondents knowledge on drug use for the treatment of urinary schistosomiasis

Treatments	Number of respondents	Percentage
Ampiclox	12	4.5
Dapsone	12	4.5
Herbs	21	7.9
No idea	219	83.0
Total	264	100.0

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Knowledge on transmission of urinary schistosomiasis

The study documented the knowledge on the causes, treatments and health seeking-behaviour of Kiri community in Shelleng Local Government area of Adamawa State whose livelihood depend majorly on fishing at Kiri dam. Respondents knowledge on the causes of urinary schistosomiasis was not satisfactory as less than fifty percent of the respondents correctly knew the cause of the disease, especially bathing in contaminated water. The knowledge was highly dependent on educational level since the correct cause of urinary schistosomiasis was mentioned by those of secondary level. This findings concord with other studies conducted by [20,21]. The ignorance of the people could be probably attributed to lack of health education programme on the causes of urinary schistosomiasis.

4.2 Water contacts

From the result recorded there was considerable variation between males and females with regard to water contacts each day with male having higher percentage than females. This could be attributed to contact activities such as fishing, swimming and bathing by males in which case females were restricted. It was observed that water contact rates among females within the age groups of 16-20 year, 21-25 years and 26-30 years were higher, and least in age groups between 0-5 years and >30 years. The higher water contact rates within these age groups could be probably due to different activities with water such as laundry, fishing and fetching for domestic purposes. The reason for the lower water contact rates among age group 0-5 years may be because they are too young to be involved in water activities since majority of this age group could only go to the dam in company of their parents or their seniors. Those >30 years probably consider themselves as too old to be involved in water activities. The fact that male respondents of age bracket of 16-20 years had higher contact rates with water was not surprising because it was this same age group that go to the dam more frequently for fishing.

4.3 Health-care seeking behaviour

The health-seeking behaviour of the respondents in relation to urinary schistosomiasis showed that they preferred visiting patent medicine store for treatment of

the disease, and considered the most effective medical intervention as evidenced in their choice of health-seeking behaviour. Others preferred going to the hospital probably they had more confidence in hospital compared to other health facilities. Some respondents preferred traditional treatment. Probably because the traditional herbs were more assessable than orthodox treatment as residents travel for a long distance before reaching the hospital. Interestingly, the World Health Organization recommended that herbal medicine could be use as an alternative medicine where health care services is not available [22]. A higher percentage of the population do not seek for treatment in urinary schistosomiasis infection. This may not be unconnected with the level of ignorance displayed on the pathology of urinary schistosomiasis among the residents, in addition to poverty that could make them not to afford the cost of obtaining proper medical care.

The higher rate (83.0%) of ignorance on the knowledge of drug used for the treatment of urinary schistosomiasis indicated high level of uneducated people among the residents. Education has been known to improve knowledge, this is the reason why the causes of urinary schistosomiasis were better explained by respondents of secondary level. Ampicolox and Dapsone (4.5% each) were mentioned by the respondents as drug they knew for the treatment of urinary schistosomiasis contrary to praziquantel as the drug of choice for the treatment of the disease. This is a proof to show that proprietors of patent medicine store and drug vendors where such medications are obtained by the residents neither new the treatment of urinary schistosomiasis. Again, it is probably that the patent medicine store owners and drug vendors were unable to differentiate urinary tract infection from urinary schistosomiasis. There is the need to educate the drug vendors and patent medicine store owners, the point at which people in rural communities get their medication for the treatment of the disease.

This study will develop concise method that will carry message on the transmission of urinary schistosomiasis. The findings will be used for proper health education and planning to reduce to the bearest minimum urinary schistosomiasis among Kiri community.

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